

Impact of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance in Nigeria

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Abstract: Most organizations put more efforts on the focus of only intrinsic and extrinsic reward systems but give less concern on the traditional cultural activities. Organization culture has received relatively low levels of empirical investigation among the possible antecedents of employee performance. Although empirical research has been carried out, there has been little evidence to prove the effect of organization culture on organization performance. The study thus examined the impact of organizational culture on employee performance. Ordinary least square (OLS) simple regression method of analysis was employed to examine the extent to which Employee Involvement, Consistency, and organizational mission, has impacted on Job efficiency, Job effectiveness, Job productivity. Findings from study revealed that Consistency as a factor of organizational culture was found to be a significant predictor of job effectiveness. Organizations mission was also found to have a significant impact on Job efficiency in Nigeria. The study finally revealed that there is a direct and significant relationship between Employee involvement and employee job productivity. The study thus suggests that every organization should carry out regular appraisals to determine the performance of its employees; and the organization can take the said opportunity to address the shortfalls and help the employees unleash their full potentials. The full responsibility of strengthening organizational culture lies entirely with the management and it is therefore recommended that the organization invests in training and development of its employees to improve their human capability at all levels.

Keywords: Organization culture, organizational mission, Employee Involvement, Consistency, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is very necessary for an organization to establish an organizational culture to maintain its position in market. The organizational culture has to be developed to provide support to an organization and bring continuous improvement. The culture of an organization is very important for the progress of an organization because it impacts on employee commitment and their retention as well. If the culture of an organization is flexible it will provide such working environment to employees in which they may work easily and independently without feeling any burden. Every organization wants employee commitment because it is very important for an organizational effectiveness. If the employees understand the organizational culture properly so that there may be improvement in their performance the reason is that the employee's performance is the base of an organization. Organizational outcomes and success is derived by the individual contribution in the organization at all levels. If every individual performs according to the expected standards then organizational performance will be enhanced. It is for this reason that job performance is considered an extremely important criterion that translates into organizational outcomes and success; making it the backbone of every organization.

Armstrong and Baron (1998), consider a number of factors in measuring employee job performance. One of them is the level of productivity of an employee, which is measured by the extent to which the employee produces the desired quality and quantity of assignments. Another measure of employee performance is the extent to which one demonstrates ability to clearly define solutions to problem areas. An employee's ability to complete projects within deadlines and other time-sensitive expectations is another measure of their performance (Cascio, 2006). According to Cascio (2006), competency and efficiency are also crucial factors considered while measuring the employee's job performance. While competency measures the extent to which an employee demonstrates his/her ethical business practices and consistency between his/her values and performance, efficiency measures how effectively streamlined an employee's production facilities are in terms of the steps he/she needs to perform in order to accomplish a task (Cascio, 2006). Teamwork, that is how well an employee works in a team setting, and communication skills—the ability of an employee to share information with their coworkers, customers and employer—are also key in measuring employee performance. Cascio (2006) cites other employee job performance indicators like job skills, an employee's work relationships, level of adaptability, self-motivation, creativity, stress tolerance among other factors.

The concept of organizational culture, in particular, has been generating a lot of interest in both research and practice in recent times. It has so far attracted significant interest in both the academic and business world because of a tantalizing promise: that culture may be a key to enhancing financial performance (Siehl and Martin, 1990). Organizational culture is a set of different value system which can help an organization to run itself and run a successful business Schhneider (1983). Organizational culture helps employees to understand the functioning of the organizations by sharing its norms, values and rules and regulation of organization (Deshpande and Webster, 1989). According to (Lok & Crawford, 2004) organizational culture has remarkable effect on employee's commitment and performance. If the employees of the organization have more understanding with the organizational culture they will have more job Satisfaction (Chang and Lee, 2007). O'Reilly and Chatman's (1991) defined organization culture is a setup of behavior, attitude and values. According to Herzberg (1959) in his study, job satisfaction is a part of employee job. If it affects positively, it motivate employee to job satisfaction otherwise it leads to job dissatisfaction. Job satisfaction is emotional ability of employee related to positive and negative aspect of its job experiences Locke (1969). Environment of organization and employee's personal traits can influence its job satisfaction Seasohore and Taber (1975). A committed employee is the person who stay with the organization in tough condition and try to fulfill the organizational goals, Meyer and Allen (1997), cited in Rashid, Sambasivan & Johari 2003. According to Silverthorne (2004) organizational culture and employee performance has strong relationship, but organizations with negative organizational culture faces lack of employee commitment.

Despite of so much researches and studies there is contradiction about the impact of organizational culture on employee performance because it provides no such reasonable relationship between organizational culture and employee performance, the various studies based on empirical evidence have come as contradictory results about the impact of organizational culture on employee job effectiveness and efficiency. As there is much contradiction in results the question is that either organizational culture enhances the employee performance or not. So there is further need to research to cover this gap mostly researches have been conducted in developing countries.

1.1 Statement of the Problem:

Most organizations put more efforts on the focus of only intrinsic and extrinsic reward systems give less concern on the traditional cultural activities. According to Kandula (2006) the key to good performance is a strong culture. He further maintains that due to difference in organizational culture, same strategies do not yield same results for two organizations in the same industry and in the same location. A positive and strong culture can make an average individual performance and achieve brilliantly whereas a negative and weak culture may demotivate an outstanding employee to underperform and end up with no achievement. Therefore organizational culture has an active and direct role in performance management (Ahmed, 2012). Organizational culture is correlated with job satisfaction (Sharma & Bajpai, 2010), job performance and employee retention (Anis et al. 2011).

However, organization culture has received relatively low levels of empirical investigation among the possible antecedents of employee performance (Lok & Crawford, 2004). Although empirical research has been carried out there has been little evidence to prove the effect of organization culture on organization performance (Mckinono et al. 2003). In a study of Hong Kong and Australian managers, Lok and Crawford (2004) found a positive effect of organization culture

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on employee performance. Zain et al. (2009) examined the effect of four dimensions of organization culture namely teamwork, communication, reward and recognition, and training and development on employee performance and found that all the four dimensions of organization culture were important determinants of performance. Mahmudah (2012) reports a significant relationship between organization culture and service delivery. However Lahiry (1994) indicated a weak association between organization culture and performance.

Concerns have been raised on whether there are any significant relationships between the culture in organizations and employee burnout, type of coping strategies, and employee engagement. Whether there is an inverse relationship between emotional exhaustion and organizational culture (Yousef, 2000). Management of human resources may perhaps force not merely the restructuring of cultural values but to consider the overture of different cultural practices which perhaps leads to a superior organizational performance.

This attempts to analyze the extent an organizations culture has an effect on employee performance in Aso savings and loan organization

1.2 Research Questions:

- i. What relationship exists between consistency as an element of organizational culture and employee job effectiveness?
- ii. To what extent has organization's mission as an element of organizational culture has significantly influenced employee efficiency?
- iii. To what extent has employee involvement as an element of organizational culture impacted on employee job productivity?

1.3 Statement of Hypotheses:

Hypotheses for this research are stated in a null form as shown below:

Hypothesis one:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between consistency as an element of organizational culture and employee job effectiveness

Hypothesis Two:

H₀₂: Organization's mission as an element of organizational culture has not significantly influenced the influence employee job efficiency

H₀₃: Employee involvement as an element of organizational culture has no significant impact on employee job productivity

2. LITERATURE REVIEW: CONCEPT, THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL REVIEW**2.1 Concepts of Organizational Culture:**

Organizational culture is literally described by many researchers in diverse studies for various measures. According to Nongo (2012) asserted that culture is critical to understanding any society or group. Through the process of socialization individuals bring into groups. Groups have the capacity to shape, influence, and determine group members' outlooks, viewpoints, outputs, attitudes and indeed behaviors.

Organizations are created to solve societal problems. So that organizations employ individuals to assist them in the task of solving their assigned societal problems. However the behavioral border among organizational members creates a pattern of behaviors, values and attitudes that can be distinguished, isolated and identified as strange organizational culture. And the researcher measured organizational culture the in term of involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission and employee performance measured in profitability, productivity, and employee motivation. On other hand, Mehr (2012) stated that today cultural clashes in any international project organization have led to an increased emphasis on preparedness on possible conflicts existing in cross-cultural cooperation. Cultural differences often result in varying degrees of conflict and require careful consideration.

For a business, organizational culture is either a force for change or a definite barrier to it; hence managers are increasingly challenged with changing an organization's culture to support new ways of accomplishing work. According to Nelson & Quick, (2011), organizational culture performs four functions: gives members a sense of identity, increases their commitment, reinforces organizational value and serves as a control mechanism for shaping behavior. It is important to note that leaders shape and reinforce culture by what they pay attention to, how they behave, how they allocate rewards and how they hire and fire individuals.

However, corporate culture is an important factor in enhancing the attainment of organizational goals and objectives. And corporate culture affects the way in which people behave in an organization and also corporate culture can lead the employee improvement in workplaces to help and become more committed to their jobs (Nongo & Ikyanyon1, 2012). And the researcher measured corporate culture the variables include: involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission on employee commitment to the organization.

In contrary to, Lim(1995) defined the term "culture" refers broadly to a relatively stable set of beliefs, values and behaviors commonly held by a society. And despite the claims for a link between organizational culture and corporate performance, few studies appear to have actually examined the existence as well as the nature of this relationship.

Garmendia (2004) discussed that a strong culture is now nearly generally understood to have a positive impact on performance. The translation of observation to the association between strong culture and success would involve playing down the importance of the former, so as to avoid an implied defense of cultural determinism. Certainly, financial results themselves influence cultural strength. Moreover, performance depends on many variables, and may therefore be found to be very high in companies with weak cultures.

The definitions and the measurements of the organizational culture discussed in the previous sections are consistent according to the context in which this study is conducted. Therefore, researchers of this study will measure the organizational culture in term of involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission as already adopted by Nongo (2012).

2.2 Theoretical Review:

The theoretical review will cover the below theories related to performance and organisation culture. This study is based majorly on the Consistency Theory, Involvement Theory, mission theory and Adaptability Theory. Other theory discussed are; the Schein's theory of organisational culture, Theory X and Theory Y by McGregor, and the theory of Open-Book Management by John Stack. Theories of organizational culture attempt to explain the phenomena that occur in and around individuals. The conceptual study regarding organizational culture is often called the phenomenon of interest. Rather than a mathematical formula, the study of organizational culture includes shared understanding, intangible values and assumptions, and the effects culture has on human behavior. Understanding the phenomenon of organizational culture allows companies to strengthen their working environments.

The study of theories of organizational culture is often difficult due to the lack of concrete evidence on various cultures. A shared understanding of organizational culture is one of the different theories among private and public sector organizations. Individuals in a company often hire like-minded individuals in order to promote a specific, well-defined purpose. This allows the business or organization to have a singular focus in terms of Performance. Theories on organizational culture typically have different overall corporate mind-sets, such as ethics, profits, or philanthropy. The shared characteristics only change through time when hiring managers replace older workers (Ojo, 2008)

2.2.1 Consistency Theory:

According to the consistency theory, organizations tend to be effective because they have strong cultures that are highly consistent, well-coordinated and well integrated (Davenport, 1993; Saffold 1988). Employee behavior is rooted in a set of core values and leaders and followers are skilled at reaching an agreement even when they have differing views (Blois, Cook & HunSaker(2007). This type of consistency is a powerful source of stability and internal integration that results from a common mindset and a high degree of conformity (Senge, 1990).

2.2.2 Involvement Theory:

This theory is based on the idea that involvement and participation will contribute to a sense of responsibility and ownership and hence organizational performance and loyalty (Baker, 2002). Effective organizations empower their people, build their organizations around teams, and develop human capability at all levels (Baker 2004). Executives, managers and employees are committed to their work and feel that they own a piece of the organization. People at all levels feel that they have at least some input into decisions that will affect their work and that their work is directly connected to the goals of the organization.

2.2.3 Adaptability Theory:

This theory is based on the idea that norms and beliefs that enhance an organization's ability to receive, interpret and translate signals from the environment into internal organizational and behavioral changes will promote its survival, growth and development. Ironically, organizations that are well integrated are often the most difficult ones to change due to the deep levels of adaptability acquired over time (Kanter, 1993). Adaptable organizations are driven by their customers, take risks and learn from their mistakes and have the capability and experience at creating change (Nadler, 1998; Senge, 1990). Such organizations are continuously changing their systems to promote improvements and provide value for their customers (Stalk, 1988).

2.2.4 Mission Theory:

A shared sense of purpose, direction and strategy can coordinate and galvanize organizational members toward collective goals (Baker, 2004). Successful organizations have a clear sense of purpose and direction that defines organizational goals and strategic objectives and expresses a vision of how the organization will look in the future (Mintzberg, 1994). When an organization's underlying mission changes, changes also occur in other aspects of the organization's culture (Ahmad, 2012). These theories focus on different aspects of culture but more importantly, they stress different functions of culture. Consistency theory and mission theory tend to promote stability whereas involvement theory and adaptability theory allow for change and adaptability. Consistency theory and involvement theory see culture as focusing on internal organizational dynamics while mission theory and adaptability theory see culture as addressing the relation of the organization to its external environment (Baker, 2004).

2.3 Empirical Reviews on Organizational Culture and Employee's Performance:

Many researchers investigated the relationship between organizational culture and performance. Studies have shown that the relationship between many cultural attributes and employees' performance has not been consistent over time (Denison, 2015). Lunenburg (2011) investigated the relationship between organizational culture and performance and stated that organizational culture is the set of shared values, beliefs, and norms that influence the way employees think, feel, and behave in the workplace. An organization's culture can have an impact on organizational effectiveness. And the author adopted Peters and Waterman generalized concept of excellence. They identified several attributes that characterize excellent organizations: a bias toward action; close to the customer; autonomy and entrepreneurship; productivity through people; hands-on, value driven effort; sticking to the knitting; simple form, lean staff; and simultaneous loose-tight properties. And also, the author adopted Theory Z which was developed by William Ouchi (1980) as an approach to excellence.

And the features of Theory Z which apply to schools include the following: trust, subtlety, and intimacy; shared control and decision making; skills training; motivation through self-interest; equitable reward system; and quality education. And the researcher recommended the following suggestions. First, knowing the culture of an organization allows employees to understand both the organization's history and current methods of operation. Second, organizational culture can foster commitment to the organization's philosophy and values.

Third, organizational culture, through its norms, serves as a control mechanism to channel behaviors toward desired behaviors and away from undesired behaviors. Finally, certain types of organizational cultures may be related directly to greater effectiveness and productivity than others (Lunenburg, 2011).

Marcoulides and Heck (2013) researched the Organizational Culture and Performance: Proposing and Testing a Model concerning how an organization's culture affects organizational performance. And demonstrate the application of LISREL modeling methodology to estimate and test this model. And hypothesized three interrelated dimensions: a socio-cultural system of the perceived functioning of the organization's strategies and practices, an organizational value system, and the collective beliefs of the individuals working within the organization. The researcher measured organizational culture by several latent variables which are: organizational structure and purpose, organizational values, task organization, climate, and individual values and beliefs.

Ojo (2011) examined various concepts on organizational culture and strives to ascertain the importance of relationship between organizational culture and corporate performance in business context. The study adopted survey research design. The researcher chose Nigerian employees in commercial banking industry as population of his study. The researcher's findings drawn that organizational culture plays a vital role in an organization's general performance.

Aluko (2013) examined that there a significantly positive relationship between organizational culture and employee's performance, and found that an organizations and its employees were not performing and working together very well because of weak culture. The organization's weak culture may cause lack of involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission.

2.3.1 Organizational Mission and Employee Job Performance:

From the discussion above, we see that it takes effort for an organization to establish an explicit, highly distinctive culture that stands out from the crowd. Achua and Lussier (2013) note that a unique corporate culture provides value to the organization and, therefore, hard to duplicate or imitate. In this regard, it helps to build and sustain a firm's competitive advantage. For this to happen, the organization has to have a mission statement and values that have meaning; a statement that people will take seriously; a set of overarching beliefs that serve as powerful guides for everyday action—and that are reinforced in a hundred different ways, both symbolic and substantive.

Organizations that value innovation encourage high employee job performance because by so doing, it promotes competition among the employees. This will make every other employee in that organization to bring out their best in order to stand out and receive rewards and recognition.

An organizational mission is an organization's reason for existence (Sorensen, 2002). It is sometimes referred to as a creed, purpose, or statement of corporate philosophy and values (Forest and David 2003). The mission of an organization is aligned to the expectations of its targeted customers, so as to achieve its ultimate returns (Zhang, Li and Pan, 2009). It often reflects the values and beliefs of top managers in an organization. It, therefore, all starts with the organizations' leaders to define these values and then help the employees discover how their personal values are validated when they perform their jobs in accordance with the organizational values. This alignment, asserts Gordon (2008), will make personal and corporate values increase staff engagement. Therefore, employees gain more fulfillments from their job and are motivated to work harder, bringing their best to their work. Runy (2007) concurs, adding that a high-performing organization has a committed workforce that is aligned with mission, vision and values and is motivated to achieve organizational objectives. Achua and Lussier (2013) affirm that culture offers a shared understanding about the identity of an organization. The right culture can make employees feel that they are valued participants and, as such, become self-motivated to take on the challenge of realizing the organization's mission and work together as a team. It can transform an organization's workforce into a source of creativity and innovative solutions.

2.3.2 Culture of Involvement and Employee Job Performance:

Involvement in this context is to be understood as a regular participation of employees in deciding how their work is done, making suggestions for improvement, goal-setting, planning, and monitoring of their performance (Macleod and Brady, 2008). A performance culture is built around shared desire to exceed expectations and achieve remarkable results. However, this starts with individuals. Organizations with high performing cultures, notes Achua and Lussier (2013), see their employees as their number one asset. They treat employees with dignity and respect, grant them greater autonomy, involve them in decision-making, celebrate individual and team achievements, and use a full range of rewards and punishment to enforce high performance standards (Achua and Lussier 2013)

According to Zhang, Li and Pan (2009), organizations that uphold an involvement culture emphasize the input and participation of its members. These organizations, therefore, make their members become highly concerned about organizational immediate interests and increase the cohesion, so they can easily reach agreement in existing challenges.

One way of enhancing employee job performance is by involving them in the organization's decision-making—at least to a level that they are allowed (Manyonyi 2012). There are decisions that require secrecy due to their nature, and this is understandable, but there are others that should involve employees in an organization. These decisions, Manyonyi (2012) advises, should be made with the participation of the people they affect; this means consulting them or having a discussion in order to get their views and generate new ideas. An organization with a culture of involving its employees will tend to perform well because the employees will own the decision, and, therefore, hold themselves responsible in case of any failure. It's easy to get so swept away thinking of solutions in board meetings that managers forget to consult the people who matter: the employees (Bakker, Schaufeli, Leiter, and Taris, 2008). The results can be surprising. Anderson (2012) reveals that a few years ago, Kwik Fit Insurance Company asked its call centre staff what would make them happier at work.

According to Orpen (2015), employee empowerment can be an integral element of organizational culture change in that it embodies the concepts of intrinsic motivation, internal justification for decision-making, shared responsibilities, and integration for problem solving. As employees mature in an organization, they gain more knowledge, internalize justification for the actions they take, and become more intrinsically motivated. Alongside this internalization process, employees tend to take a more active role in intervening in the actions of newer employees and offering feedback regarding culture-consistent behaviors. When employees are empowered, they feel motivated to work because then nothing holds them back as they know what is expected of them and are competent in their duties.

More open forms of participative management give workers decision-making authority regarding their domains of responsibility (Macey 2009). When companies shift to the more open forms of participative management, they begin the process of empowering their employees. Kurstedt, Harold and Mallak, (1996) assert that an organization's level of empowerment is related to its culture. A strong culture supports the empowerment process in many ways. First, companies with strong cultures provide continuity and clarity with respect to their missions. Second, companies with strong cultures minimize mixed signals because they have reduced ambivalence in their communications, and management tends to speak with one voice. Third, companies with strong cultures have a central core of consistency that drives the basic decision-making processes throughout the organization. This central core promotes consistency regarding basic values and beliefs, yet allows for individual interpretations and responses for items outside the central core. Fourth, strong culture firms help employees build —social currency| based on track record, reputation, knowledge, and network of relationships. This social currency builds communication and trust and provides the power to get things done independent of formal titles and authority.

Manyonyi (2012) emphasizes that an organization that effectively communicates information to its employees and makes it accessible to its employees makes them feel part of the organization. This makes employees want to do their best not just for their paycheck, but for the organization. The kinds of information that can be transmitted to employees include: the long-term plans of the organization and new developments such as opportunities or problems faced by the company.

Another way of establishing a culture of involvement in an organization is by incentivizing employees so as to increase their performance. This can be by informing them of the financial position of the organization and, when possible, sharing with them the profits. Case (2013) reveals that PSS, a US-based organization, has a share-the-wealth, share-the-information culture of a sort rarely found in American business. At PSS, every employee is a shareholder where some have more than a million dollars' worth in their accounts. And there are no secrets here, as everybody knows what salespeople X, Y, and Z sold yesterday, how much gross margin each of them realized and how the branch is doing week by week and month by month, against plan.

Most employers believe that offering additional money will draw more production from their employees (Anderson 2012). Many times this is not true. What employees most often want is to know that they matter to the company or organization. Adding to their salaries, says Anderson (2012), does show them they are important, but normally this is the least effective means of increasing employee performance. It is also the most expensive. Some little gestures of recognition employed by an organization increase employee job performance. Multinational organizations for example,

put up a map on the wall of the staff canteen. When people join the company, they put a pin on the country they are from. This makes the new employee feel welcome to the team, and is good for communication. Organizations that have a culture of celebrating birthdays, organizing get-togethers, whether it's paintballing sessions or a small glass of wine in the staff room at the end of an afternoon, helping a charity is another way to give workers a common purpose and a feel-good factor (Macleod and Brady 2008).

DeWitt (2010) asserts that organizations that have a culture of recognizing for a job well done boost morale and offer a greater sense of achievement. The moment employees understand that they are appreciated and that their efforts matter beyond earning a paycheck, performance will normally increase. Regular times of recognition in small or simple ways can help employees know their value and increase their performance.

Another strong trait of organizational culture that enhances high performance among employees in an organization is team work. Xenikou and Simosi, (2006) say that organizational norms that encourage cooperation, teamwork, and participation are related to performance because they facilitate group coordination and synergy of divergent organizational resources. He adds that moreover, self-actualization and employee development are the basis of creating a large pool of organizational resources that reflect the human capital within organizations and lead to organizational efficiency.

2.3.4 Organizational Consistency and Employee Job Performance:

Consistency implies the extent to which the values, beliefs and standards of behavior are acquired and shared among employees in an organization (Denison 2009). Organizational culture defines a normative order that serves as a source of consistent behavior inside an organization (Achua and Lussier, 2013). Consistency culture, in fact, is a theory of strong culture. According to Zhang, Li and Pan (2009), consistency culture in an organization is manifested by widely shared beliefs and values that help organizational members to reach consensus and take concerted action, so as to have a positive impact on performance. Such a high degree of unity within an organization adds Zhang, Li and Pan (2009), can save on manpower, materials, financial and other resources, whilst boosting performance.

An organization will operate more productively as a whole when key values are shared among the majority of its members. To that end, employees need to be comfortable with the behaviors encouraged by the organization so that individual motivation and group productivity remain high. High functioning organizations are comprised of individuals whose overt behaviors are consistent with their covert values (Khan, 2015). All of this is of crucial importance to managers. Senior executives usually set the tone by exerting core values that form the overall dominant culture shared by the majority of an organization's members. So, if management does not take the time to understand the culture that motivates an organization, problems are inevitable. New procedures and activities will be very difficult to implement if they do not mesh with the organization's culture.

A culture of consistency is created by leaders in the organization who are meant to be role models. According to Achua and Lussier (2013) the stories leaders tell, the decisions they make, and the actions they take reveal an implicit cultural expectation for followers. Employees learn what is valued most in an organization by watching what attitudes and behaviors leaders pay attention to and whether the leaders' own behavior is consistent with organizational values. Again, as leaders who have the voice of the organization, they must be sure to communicate clear expectations for every member of the organization. These expectations should be supported by the words and actions of managers who regularly let people know how their work is important to the organization.

Another technique of creating a consistent culture in an organization lies with the top management. In order to promote a culture of consistency, leaders can design the physical work environment to reflect the values they want to promote within the organization (Achua and Lussier 2013). The authors give an example of having common eating facilities for all employees, no special parking areas and similar offices is consistent with the value of equality; an open office layout with fewer walls separating employees is consistent with the value for open communication. In designing its headquarters, Google provided open workspaces and an environment that provided coworker contact and interaction. By providing a clear sense of place and purpose for its employees, Google succeeded in communicating an employee-friendly culture through its facility design, with the architecture and comfort of the setting reinforced by the cultural and aesthetic elements in the building. This, in turn, improved employee job performance.

According to Kotter and Heskett (2012) leaders who plan most of the work should give individuals assignments that are consistent with their strengths and interests and opportunities for continued learning and growth. Gordon (2008) asserts that organizational values, which form part of the corporate culture, greatly aid to facilitate the recruiting process. How does recruitment relate to consistency? Serious organizations have a particular way of recruiting; this depends on their kind of business. At recruiting, there is a particular trait organizations are looking for. For an organization to maintain its high performance culture, it has to be consistent in how it recruits—hiring only the best with specific qualifications.

Consistency can also be looked at from the point of view of the organization and employee as far as values and purpose are concerned. If there is consistency in values between the two, then there is a match. Khan (2015) asserts that the degree to which an organization's values match the values of an individual who works for the company determines whether a person is a good match for a particular organization. He (Khan) advises that it is important for individual values to match organization culture because a culture of —shared purpose^l results in actions that help the organization achieve a common or collective goal.

Consistency, as an element of organizational culture cements positive aspects in an organization hence helps establish a strong culture which, by extension, leads to a high performance organization. There is no doubt that organizations with a strong corporate culture have an almost unfair competitive head start (Rahid, Sambasivan and Johari 2003). Employees in such organizations have reasons to care about how they perform. Even the challenges presented by mind-bending change—whether imposed by the marketplace or necessitated by internal growth—are easier to handle because a stable culture begets a fast-moving, flexible company (Gordon, 2008).

With the fast-changing business environment, organizations undergo a lot of change in order to be relevant and stay competitive in the labor market. With such changes, organizations are forced to develop new product lines, enter new markets, and introduce new technology. Where do these changes leave the employee? In weak and inconsistent cultures, employees will find such moves unsettling, even unnerving. A strong, distinctive culture, however, will offer a fixed reference point. Quoting Rosabeth Moss Kanter of Harvard Business School, Case (1996) equates a strong culture to an anchor for letting people lose to create a lot of change and not what impedes change (Case, 1996).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design:

A research design provides the framework to be used as a guide in collecting and analyzing data (Cooper and Schindler, 2001). The study assumed a descriptive research design that was triangulated with both qualitative and quantitative tools of analysis. A descriptive design was used because it helps describe characteristics associated with the subject population and explain the variables that exist between these variables in order to provide a picture of a particular phenomenon (Cooper and Schindler, 2003).

3.2 Method of Data Analysis:

Data analysis method entailed editing, coding and tabulation of data collected into manageable summaries. To ensure easy analysis, the questionnaire was coded according to each variable of the study to ensure accuracy during analysis. This analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), E-views and MS Excel. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, which include frequencies and percentages and the OLS regression method. These tools of analysis were used, for instance, to determine the relationship that exists between dependent and independent variables. Regression was used to describe the relationship between organizational culture and employee job performance in this study. This method was appropriate because as Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2003) noted, descriptive statistics enable us to describe (and compare) variables numerically. The results from the analysis were presented using tables to provide an accurate picture of the research findings.

3.3 Procedure for Data Analysis and Model Specifications:

Quantitative analysis was used for the purpose of this study. This is because quantitative analysis results provide support for anticipated directions of the association between independent and dependent variables, therefore the study used regression analysis (OLS) to address the three hypotheses of this study since the study is addressing relationship between the various variables. This was achieved by the use of E-view 7.0

The major statistical analysis that was used in this study is the ordinary least square (OLS) regression analysis- the simple regression analysis. This analysis was used in order to find the linear relationship between the independent variables.

3.4 Variable Descriptions:

- i. **Employee Involvement** is the rate of participation and initiative of all the employees in an organization (Macleod and Brady, 2008).
- ii. **Consistency** implies the extent to which the values, beliefs and standards of behavior are acquired and shared among employees in an organization (Denison, 2009). Consistent organizations, according to Denison, *et al* (2015), develop a mindset and create organizational systems that build internal systems of governance based on consensual support.
- iii. **An organizational mission** is an organization's reason for existence (Sorensen, 2002). Forest and David (2003) assert that successful organizations have a clear sense of purpose and direction that defines organizational goals and strategic objectives and expresses a vision of what the organization will look like in the future, adding that a sense of mission allows an organization to shape current behavior by envisioning a desired future state.
- iv. **Job productivity of an employee**, which is measured by the extent to which the employee produces the desired quality and quantity of assignments. Another measure of employee performance is the extent to which one demonstrates ability to clearly define solutions to problem areas. An employee’s ability to complete projects within deadlines and other time-sensitive expectations is another measure of their performance (Cascio, 2006).
- v. According to Cascio (2006), **effectiveness and efficiency** are also crucial factors considered while measuring the employee’s job performance. **While effectiveness** measures the extent to which an employee demonstrates his/her ethical business practices and consistency between his/her values and performance, **efficiency measures** how fluently streamlined an employee’s production facilities are in terms of the steps he/she needs to perform in order to accomplish a task (Cascio, 2006). Teamwork, that is how well an employee works in a team setting, and communication skills—the ability of an employee to share information with their coworkers, customers and employer—are also key in measuring employee performance. Cascio (2006) cites other employee job performance indicators like job skills, an employee’s work relationships, level of adaptability, self-motivation, creativity, stress tolerance among other factors.

3.5 Model Specification:

The model specifications here are formulated to tests the three hypotheses and they are as follows:

$$JEV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 C + \mu_t \text{-----} 1$$

$$JEF = \beta_0 + \beta_2 OM + \mu_t \text{-----} 2$$

$$JP = \beta_0 + \beta_3 EI + \mu_t \text{-----} 3$$

Where;

- JEF = Job efficiency
- JEV = Job effectiveness
- JP = Job productivity
- OM = Organization Mission
- EI = Employee Involvement
- C = Consistency

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Data Presentation:

Table 1: Data Summary

Variables	Items	Agreement scale				
		SD(%)	D(%)	U(%)	A(%)	SA(%)
<i>Job efficiency</i>	Activities and task given are efficiently carried in due to time	4.4	4.6	5.4	25	60.7
	More customers has been attracted due to proper time management in the bank	6.2	3.7	7.1	44.6	37.5
	New technologies has been adopted by the bank staff for efficient discharge of duties	5.3	6.1	2.7	55.5	28.5
<i>Job effectiveness</i>	More returns has been accrued in the bank due to job effectiveness	12.4	2.7	15.2	43.8	25
	The operations of the bank are adequately carried out without complications	6.3	7.1	2.7	54.5	29.5
	Competitive capacity of organizations can be increased by building strong people and effectively managing them	11.6	7.1	9.8	45.2	26.2
<i>Job productivity</i>	The number of hours worked has been reduced to boost effectiveness	5.3	3.7	5.4	24	61.7
	Most challenging task given are carried out without much stress	6.3	7.1	2.7	54.5	29.5
	Most of the customers issue are resolved within the turnaround time and before close of business	5.4	3.6	5.4	22.4	60.7
<i>Organization Mission</i>	The culture of your organization is open to change. You are able to react and adapt quickly, and are open to new ideas.	7.3	6.1	2.7	55.5	28.5
	Organizational culture acts as the _social glue ‘that bonds people together and makes them feel part of the organizational experience.	11.6	7.1	9.8	45.2	26.2
	Top managers help me discover how my personal values are validated when I perform my job in accordance with the organizational values.	5.4	3.6	5.4	25	60.7
	During the interview, some of the questions I was asked presented the organization’s cultural values.	5.3	6.1	2.7	55.5	28.5
	The organizational values are aligned along the expectations of our targeted customers.	5.4	3.6	5.4	25	60.7
	The company employs people who share the same values and vision that the organization represents.	11.6	8.1	8.8	48.2	23.2
<i>Employee Involvement</i>	My organization empowers and engages me.	13.4	8.9	10.7	53.6	13.4
	My organization encourages some input into decisions that affect my work.	11.2	8.1	8.8	48.2	23.2
	My organization continually invests in the development of its employee’s skills in order to remain competitive and meet on-going business needs.	5.3	3.7	5.4	24	61.7
	My organization places much value on employees working cooperatively towards the common goals of the organization.	5.3	6.1	2.7	55.5	28.5
	The employee involvement in my organization is informal, voluntary and does not involve implicit control systems.	5.4	3.6	5.4	25	60.7
<i>Consistency</i>	I share a set of attributes which create a sense of identity with my organization.	11.6	8.1	8.8	48.2	23.2
	As an employee, am given assignments that are consistent with my strengths, interests and opportunities.	5.3	3.7	5.4	24	61.7
	High functioning organizations are comprised of individuals whose overt behaviours are consistent with their covert values.	6.3	7.1	2.7	54.5	29.5
	My values and behaviors are consistent with those of my organization.	5.4	3.6	5.4	22.4	60.7

Source: Computed by the Author (SPSS and Excel)

4.2 Pre-Estimation Diagnostics Test:

4.2.1 Normality Statistics (Descriptive Statistics):

The normality statistics for the variables: JEF, JET, JP, OM, EI, and Care all different. This indicates that the variables exhibit significant variation in terms of magnitude, suggesting that estimation of the variables in levels may introduce some bias in the results. It could be observed that OM has the highest mean value of 17.00, followed by C with a mean value of 10.76. EI has a mean value of 8.42; JET was found to have the lowest mean value of 6.42.

Following the skewness values, JEF, JET, JP, EI, and C are all negatively skewed to the left of the normal distribution curve. However, only BE was found to be positively skewed with a value 0.037.

The Jarque-Bera statistics for the variables shows that all the variables are less than one, going by the probability values and are significant at 5%; hence we may reject the null hypothesis and state that the series are normally distributed (or have a normal distribution).

Table 2: Summary of Normality Statistics

	JEF	JET	JP	OM	EI	C
Mean	10.14775	6.423671	8.106866	17.00252	8.429763	10.76625
Median	10.33187	7.619994	8.516517	16.84358	8.858346	11.01442
Maximum	11.99782	8.714308	9.240021	18.29167	9.679790	12.75737
Minimum	8.205191	2.493205	6.145258	15.71964	6.170865	8.659665
Std. Dev.	1.071327	2.410299	1.117729	0.968542	1.310357	1.298575
Skewness	-0.476631	-0.732987	-0.599330	0.037790	-0.628331	-0.233261
Kurtosis	2.836967	1.966041	1.890414	1.506456	1.861275	2.045618
Jarque-Bera	0.506614	1.743164	1.445149	1.211376	1.557775	0.611265
Probability	0.006229	0.018289	0.045501	0.045699	0.058916	0.036657
Sum	131.9207	83.50772	105.3893	221.0327	109.5869	139.9613
Sum Sq. Dev.	13.77291	69.71447	14.99182	11.25687	20.60444	20.23557
Observations	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Authors computation, 2016

4.3 Model Evaluation and Test of Hypothesis:

The three hypotheses formulated in this study were tested using student t-statistics. The level of significance for the study is 5%, for a two tailed test. The decision rule is that we shall accept the null hypothesis if the critical/t-value (± 1.96) is greater than the calculated value, otherwise reject the null hypothesis. That is, using the student t-test (t-statistic), we say that a variable is statistically significant if t^* (t-calculated) is greater than the tabulated value of ± 1.96 under 95% (or 5%) confidence levels and it is statistically insignificant if the t^* is less than the tabulated value of ± 1.96 under 95% (or 5%) confidence levels. Thus;

$H_0: \beta_0 = 0$ (Null hypothesis)

$H_1: \beta_1 \neq 0$ (Alternative hypothesis)

4.3.1 Hypotheses One: H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between consistency as an element of organizational culture and employee job effectiveness:

Model one: $JEV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 C + \mu_t$ -----4

Table 3: Regression Result on JE and C

Stepwise Regression Analyses of Consistency on Outcome Variables				
Dependent Variable: Job effectiveness $R^2 = 0.45; F = 12.50; Sig = 0.0066$				
Independent Variable	Beta	t-value	Pearson Correlation(r)	Probability value
<i>Consistency</i>	2.12	1.98	0.75189	0.0021

Source: Authors Computation, E-Views, 7.0

$$JEV = 2.12 + 2.14C \text{-----} 5$$

$$SEE = 0.56 \quad 0.21$$

$$t^* = 7.83 \quad 1.98$$

$$F^* = 12.50; \text{Prob (F-statistic)} = 0.0066$$

$$R^2 = 0.55; \text{Adj.}R^2 = 0.46$$

$$DW = 2.01$$

Test of Hypotheses One: H_{01}

From the regression result in table 3, the calculated t-value for *Consistency* (C) is 1.98 is greater than the critical value of 1.96. It falls in the rejection region and hence, we may reject the first null hypothesis (H_{01}). The conclusion here is that *consistency has significantly enhanced job effectiveness in Nigeria.*

The ANOVA F-statistic

The F-statistics which is used to examine the overall significance of regression model equally showed that the result is significant, as indicated by a high low value of the F-statistic, 12.50 and it is significant at the 5.0 per cent level. That is, the F-statistic value of 0.0066 is less than 0.05.

The R^2 (R-square)

The R^2 (R-square) value of 0.55 shows that the Consistency has a good impact on job effectiveness (JEV). It indicates that about 55 per cent of the variation in JEV is explained by Consistency, while the remaining 45 percent is captured by the error term.

Serial correlation

The model also indicates that there is no autocorrelation among the variables as indicated by Durbin Watson (DW) statistic of 2.01. This shows that the estimates are unbiased and can be relied upon for policy decisions.

4.3.2 Hypotheses Two: Organization's mission as an element of organizational culture has not significantly influenced the influence employee job efficiency

$$\text{Model two: } JEF = \beta_0 + \beta_2 OM + \mu_t \text{-----} 6$$

Table 4: Regression result on JEF and the OM

Stepwise Regression Analyses of Organizations mission on Outcome Variables				
Dependent Variable: Job efficiency $R^2 = 0.6045; F = 14.05; Sig = 0.001$				
Independent Variable	Beta	t-value	Pearson Correlation(r)	Probability value
<i>Organizations mission</i>	2.97	2.14	0.61892	0.0431

Source: Authors Computation, 2016 (Eview-7.0)

$$JEF = 2.97 + 2.01OM \text{ -----} 7$$

$$SEE = 1.59 \quad 0.35$$

$$t^* = 2.49 \quad 2.14$$

$$F^* = 14.05; \text{Prob}(F\text{-statistic}) = 0.001$$

$$R^2 = 0.6045; \text{Adj.}R^2 = 0.5657$$

$$DW = 2.25$$

Test of Hypotheses Two: H_{02}

From table 4, the calculated t-value for **Organizations mission** is 2.14 and the tabulated value is given as ± 1.96 , under 95% confidence levels. Since the calculated t-value is greater than the tabulated value ($2.14 > 1.96$), we therefore, reject the null hypothesis (H_{02}). *We conclude that Organizations mission has significant impact on Job efficiency in Nigeria*

The ANOVA F-statistic

Also, by examining the overall fit and significance of the **Job efficiency** model, it can be observed that the model do really have relevance, as indicated by the relatively high value of the F-statistic, 14.05 and it is significant at the 5.0 per cent level. That is, the F-statistic value of 0.001 is less than 0.05 probability levels.

The R^2 (R-square)

More so, the R^2 (R-square) value of 0.6045 shows that the model does have a good fit too. It indicates that about 60.45 percent of the variation in **Organizations mission**(OM) is explained by **Job efficiency** (JE), while the remaining 49.55percent is captured by the error term.

Serial correlation

Durbin Watson (DW) statistics which is also used to test for the presence of autocorrelation indicates that there is no autocorrelation among the variables as captured by (DW) statistic of 2.25. This shows that the estimates are unbiased and can also be relied upon for policy decisions.

4.3.3 Hypothesis three: Employee involvement as an element of organizational culture has no significant impact on employee job productivity:

$$\text{Model three: } JP = \beta_0 + \beta_3EI + \mu_t \text{ -----} 8$$

Table 5: Regression result on JP and EI

Stepwise Regression Analyses of Employee involvement on Outcome Variable				
Dependent Variable: job productivity				
$R^2 = 0.6942; F = 16.33; \text{Sig} = 0.0001$				
Independent Variable	Beta	t-value	Pearson Correlation(r)	Probability value
Employee involvement	3.19	2.64	0.62145	0.0023

Source: Authors Computation, 2016 (Eview-7.0)

$$JP = 3.19 + 2.73EI \text{ -----} 9$$

$$SEE = 0.88 \quad 0.20$$

$$t^* = 4.10 \quad 2.64$$

$$F^* = 16.33; \text{Prob}(F\text{-statistic}) = 0.0001$$

$$R^2 = 0.6942; \text{Adj.}R^2 = 0.6521$$

$$DW = 2.16$$

Test of Hypotheses Three: H_{03}

The calculated t-value for **EI** was found to be 2.64 and also by rule of thumb, the tabulated value is -1.96 under 95% confidence interval levels. The calculated value of **EI** is found to be greater than the tabulated value (that is; $2.64 > 1.96$), we thus, reject the third null hypotheses (H_{03}). **In conclusion, Employee involvement had significant relationship with job productivity in Nigeria.**

The ANOVA F-statistic

Also, by examining the overall fit and significance of the **job productivity** model, it was found to have a good fit, as indicated by the high *F*-statistic value of 16.33 and it is significant at the 5.0 per cent level. That is, the *F*-statistic value of 0.0001 is less than 0.05.

The R^2 (R-square)

More so, the R^2 (R-square) value of 0.6942 shows that the model have a very good fit also. It showed that about 69.42 percent of the variation in **JP** is explained by **EI**, while the remaining 30.58 percentage unaccounted variation is captured by the error term.

Serial correlation

Durbin Watson (DW) statistics which is also used to test for the presence of serial correlation indicates that there is no autocorrelation among the variables as captured by (DW) statistic of 2.16, and as thus the estimates are unbiased and can further be relied upon for sound policy decisions.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Consistency as a factor of organizational culture was found to be a significant predictor of job effectiveness, contributing 2.12% of job effectiveness. The finding that consistency is significantly related to job effectiveness is consistent with the studies of Zhang, Li and Pan (2009), who found that consistency culture in an organization is manifested by widely shared beliefs and values that help organizational members to reach consensus and take concerted action, so as to have a positive impact on performance. Such a high degree of unity within an organization adds Zhang, Li and Pan (2009), can save on manpower, materials, financial and other resources, whilst boosting performance. A culture of consistency is created by leaders in the organization who are meant to be role models. According to Achua and Lussier (2013) the stories leaders tell, the decisions they make, and the actions they take reveal an implicit cultural expectation for followers. Employees learn what is valued most in an organization by watching what attitudes and behaviors leaders pay attention to and whether the leaders' own behavior is consistent with organizational values. Consistency, as an element of organizational culture cements positive aspects in an organization hence helps establish a strong culture which, by extension, leads to a high performance organization. There is no doubt that organizations with a strong corporate culture have an almost unfair competitive head start (Rahid, Sambasivan and Johari 2003).

The positive and significant relationship between **Organization's mission** and **employee job efficiency** is consistent with the findings of Achua and Lussier (2013) whose results showed that unique corporate culture provides value to the organization and, therefore, hard to duplicate or imitate. In this regard, it helps to build and sustain a firm's competitive advantage. For this to happen, the organization has to have a mission statement and values that have meaning; a statement that people will take seriously; a set of overarching beliefs that serve as powerful guides for everyday action—and that are reinforced in a hundred different ways, both symbolic and substantive. The mission of an organization is aligned to the expectations of its targeted customers, so as to achieve its ultimate returns (Zhang, Li and Pan, 2009). This alignment, asserts Gordon (2008), will make personal and corporate values increase staff engagement. Therefore, employees gain more fulfillments from their job and are motivated to work harder, bringing their best to their work. Runy (2007) concurs, adding that a high-performing organization has a committed workforce that is aligned with mission, vision and values and is motivated to achieve organizational objectives.

The findings finally showed that there is a direct and significant relationship between **Employee involvement** and **employee job productivity**. The results in table 4.4.3 showed that **Employee involvement** contributed 3.19% to **job**

productivity. There are empirical evidence to confirm the positive relationship between *Employee involvement* and *job productivity* in an organisation. According to Zhang, Li and Pan (2009), organizations that uphold an employee involvement culture emphasize the input and participation of its members. These organizations, therefore, make their members become highly concerned about organizational immediate interests and increase the cohesion, so they can easily reach agreement in existing challenges. One way of enhancing employee job performance is by involving them in the organization's decision-making—at least to a level that they are allowed (Manyonyi 2012). There are decisions that require secrecy due to their nature, and this is understandable, but there are others that should involve employees in an organization. These decisions, Manyonyi (2012) advises, should be made with the participation of the people they affect; this means consulting them or having a discussion in order to get their views and generate new ideas. Manyonyi (2012) emphasizes that an organization that effectively communicates information to its employees and makes it accessible to its employees makes them feel part of the organization. This makes employees want to do their best not just for their paycheck, but for the organization.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on our findings, we can conclude that employee job performance is a critical factor in every organization. It has come out clearly in this research work that knowledge is everything. One of the main reasons why employees do not perform is lack of knowledge and skills. Our study findings have shown that an organization can boost employee job performance through enhancing better communication, knowledge and understanding of tasks, and time management, among others.

The paper thus recommends that:

- i. First, we recommended that the organization carries out regular appraisals to determine the performance of its employees; the organization can take the said opportunity to address the shortfalls and help the employees unleash their full potentials. Similarly, the organization can invest in employees' capacity development through training and retreats. This will certainly boost the employees' performance.
- ii. We recommend that the management plays a pronounced role in influencing organizational culture that is aligned to its strategy and structure. This they can do by first of all themselves having a clear picture of the company's organizational culture. The management should focus more on the adherence to the organization's mission by making sure that those in leadership positions are conversant with the organization's mission so as to be able to pass it down to their subordinates. Likewise, the management should work on the ethical practices of the organization like credibility and integrity which promote a high performance culture.
- iii. The study findings revealed that the culture of involvement in the organization under study is somehow shaky. The full responsibility of strengthening this culture lies entirely with the management. We therefore recommend that the organization invests in training and development of its employees to improve their human capability at all levels. At the same time, the management should emphasize the input and participation of its employees. In order to further its employee identification with the organization, the management should extend its employee involvement in decision-making that affects them, giving them the authority and ability to manage their own work. Lastly, the artifacts, that is, tangible evidence of organizational culture like computers, employee handbook, a company logo, and corporate wares that make employees identify with the organization should be introduced.

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